

Navigating controversy and neutrality: pre-service teachers' beliefs on teaching climate change

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' climate change knowledge, beliefs, and the controversy surrounding the topic influence their curricular decisions. However, there's limited understanding of pre-service teachers' competencies and beliefs to address controversial aspects. This qualitative interview study with nine pre-service teachers in Switzerland explores their perspectives across the audience segmentation groups of *Global Warming's Six Americas* and their preparedness to teach controversial aspects. The thematic analysis revealed distinct differences. Teachers' beliefs influenced their teaching intentions, avoiding bias and controversy. Factors like inadequate pedagogical and content knowledge, the controversial nature of the topic, and perceived pressure result in teachers adopting a neutral stance. Yet, the interpretations of 'controversy' and 'neutrality' vary individually and contextually. Climate change is often approached as a scientific issue, focusing on private sphere actions, neglecting critical discussions, and hampering transformative learning. These findings highlight the importance of recognizing diverse perspectives in addressing controversial aspects – with implications for teacher education.

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Introduction

While climate change has become a major issue in science, society, and politics, research shows that teachers are reluctant to teach controversial topics such as climate change because they fear negative reactions from parents (Breitenmoser & Keller-Schneider, 2024; Nganga et al. 2020; Plutzer et al. 2016). They further state an insufficient pedagogical preparation while effective strategies for addressing controversial aspects in Climate Change Education (CCE) and supporting teachers in navigating these challenges are still scarce (Ennes et al. 2021; Nganga et al. 2020; Reid, 2019). Therefore, the role of teachers' beliefs and attitudes about controversy must be considered when examining their curricular decisions (Hess & McAvoy, 2015). The purpose of this study is to better understand how primary school pre-service teachers' climate change beliefs, attitudes, values, policy preferences, motivations, behaviours, and underlying barriers to action towards teaching controversial aspects influence their intention to teach climate change in the classroom. Specifically, our goal is to analyse how statements of pre-service primary school teachers within the audience segmentation groups according to the Global Warming's

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Six Americas differ regarding teaching controversial aspects. These climate-related attitude types have proven to be suitable for addressee-oriented climate communication (Leiserowitz et al. 2021), hence this should also apply to an addressee-oriented teacher education, considering scientific evidence and students' prior concepts and beliefs. By combining an empirically proven theoretical framework for pedagogical development (Keller-Schneider, 2020) with climate-related attitude types (Maibach et al. 2011), the unique contribution of our study is the exploration of diverse viewpoints of pre-service teachers in Switzerland when addressing controversial aspects. The following research questions were addressed in this study:

- RQ 1: What Global Warming's Six Americas attitude types are evident in the statements of the pre-service teachers studied? How do these manifest in the data?
- RQ 2: For the different groups, what do pre-service teachers say about teaching controversial aspects of climate change and which goals do they consider most relevant?
- RQ 3: What aspects do pre-service teachers see as motivations, challenges, or barriers to teaching controversial issues and how does this influence their intention to teach climate change?

Challenges of CCE

Students need to develop agency to cope with and shape a complex and uncertain future (UNESCO, 2020, 9; White et al. 2023). Transformative learning is central to developing these competencies, aligning with the objectives outlined in the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) framework (UN General Assembly, 2015). However, CCE has in the past focused strongly on spreading knowledge and teaching desirable behaviours in the private sphere, and less on the emancipatory and transformative learning processes in the public sphere (Kranz et al. 2022; Stern, 2000; Waldron et al. 2019). These would be necessary for critical engagement with complex, uncertain, and contradictory social, economic, political, and cultural interconnections of climate change (Pettig & Ohl, 2023), as a so called 'wicked problem' (Rittel & Webber, 1973). Moreover, teaching climate change is perceived as uncomfortable and hence challenging by many teachers (e.g. Colston & Vadjunec, 2015; Gayford, 2002; Monroe et al. 2019; Plutzer et al. 2016; Reid, 2019; Spiropoulou et al. 2007), partly due to the controversial portrayal of the topic in social media, news media, government, and in philanthropy (Allgaier, 2019; Farrell, 2019) despite the scientific consensus of the role of human activities in modern climate change (Lynas et al. 2021). Oulton et al. (2004) claim that only 12% of the 600 surveyed teachers feel prepared to teach controversial issues.

Approaches to teach controversy in the classroom

Previous experiences, the (social) context, and political ideologies shape learning processes (Keller-Schneider, 2020; Long et al. 2022). Teachers draw on their professional knowledge and beliefs (Blömeke, Kaiser, and Lehmann 2008) and influence children's learning success (Lipowsky, 2006). Teacher education needs to build on this knowledge and beliefs of teachers to prepare them for the challenge of teaching climate change (Brownlee et al. 2013). However, simply providing teachers with more content knowledge is not enough (e.g. Keller-Schneider, 2020; Plutzer et al. 2016; Walsh & Tsurusaki, 2014). In a qualitative study with ten (pre-service) geography teachers, Seow and Ho (2016) were able to show that teachers' beliefs about the purpose of CCE guided them in the way they included controversies in the classroom. However, Ferguson et al. (2021) concluded that so far little empirical evidence has been collected on the conceptual understanding and positioning of (pre-service) teachers on Sustainable Development (SD) and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). It often remains unclear what teachers understand

by ESD (Timm & Barth, 2021). This is significant in dealing with controversies in the sense that teachers' conceptual understanding of ESD has an impact on its implementation in the classroom (Baumann & Niebert, 2022; Boeve-de Pauw & van Petegem, 2018). According to Vare and Scott (2007), it is essential that aspects of both instrumental-anticipatory ESD 1 and critical-emancipatory ESD 2 are included in the classroom. The instrumental approach is understood as the transmission of generally accepted scientific knowledge and values, as well as individual behaviour (e.g. recycling, energy saving) in the private sphere. The emancipatory approach focusses on developing critical thinking and reflection (Vare & Scott, 2007). However, in environmental education and CCE, the focus is on private sphere actions in an ESD 1, while ESD 2 is hardly considered (Sund & Gericke, 2020). Likewise, the study results of Gaubitz (2023) showed that pre-service primary school teachers implementing ESD in the classroom voiced arguments only for an instrumental ESD 1 but against an emancipatory ESD 2. Moreover, results of an interview study with ten Singaporean teachers by Seow and Ho (2016) further suggested that teachers' beliefs about their students' academic abilities influence whether controversial issues are included in the classroom. One possible interpretation of the authors is that controversy and thus the critical handling of a variety of information is already perceived as demanding on a personal level and thus not expected of students.

Perspectives on teaching controversial climate change issues

Apart from knowledge, previous research suggested that teachers' beliefs about climate change and the presence of controversy influenced their curricular decisions (Hess, 2004; Oversby, 2015). Several factors influence the formation of beliefs about controversial issues such as climate change. These factors include psychological processes (i.e. cognitive dissonance, confirmation bias, or belief in the efficacy of individual actions), spiritual or religious beliefs about nature, views about policy and governance, social norms, and knowledge of scientific concepts and trust in scientific processes (Brownlee et al. 2013). Nation and Feldman (2021) found that teachers have strong beliefs about the causes and implications of climate change and value CCE. However, teachers' personal beliefs about climate change did influence their teaching of the curriculum in a sense, as they deliberately removed their beliefs about the issue so as not to appear biased in their teaching. Hence, they shielded their students from the controversies within the climate change dialogue. The controversial nature of climate change, the negative association of controversy with conflict (Dängeli & Kalcsics, 2018), the prevailing political climate, and opposition from parents or administrators prevented teachers from espousing their beliefs within their instruction but remaining 'neutral' and reluctant to teach controversial topics (Nganga et al. 2020). However, Plutzer et al. (2016) and Wise (2010) found in their studies that only 4.4%, respectively 15% of the teachers surveyed had experienced pressure from parents, community leaders, or school administrators not to teach about climate change. Nicholls (2016) found that Australian teachers, regardless of their position on climate change, approached it as a scientific issue rather than a complex, multi-dimensional topic in order to remain neutral. Wise (2010) and Nation and Feldman (2021) concluded that teachers present climate change as scientifically debatable and as a two-sided issue to remain neutral. The teachers intended to provide a balanced approach, presenting both sides of climate change science, and wanting to allow students to form their own opinions. Plutzer et al. (2016) conclude that most US science teachers underestimate the extent of scientific consensus about the anthropogenic driving force of climate change and therefore teach 'both sides' (Plutzer et al. 2016, 665) of the debate. In doing so, teachers did not engage students in critical discourses or debates to better understand their own and others' viewpoints necessary in emancipatory and transformative learning processes, introducing young citizens to participate in democracy (Hess & McAvoy, 2015; Kissling & Bell, 2020; Monroe et al. 2019). Likewise, there is a debate in the scientific community about teaching 'both sides' (e.g. Colston & Vadjunec, 2015; Hess & McAvoy, 2015). It is based on the question

of whether an empirical and political issue is settled or open (Hess & McAvoy, 2015, 161). Climate change is special in the sense that the issue of human-induced climate change is settled in the scientific community (Hess & McAvoy, 2015; Lynas et al. 2021). Similarly, climate change is perceived decreasingly controversial by individuals. This awareness is not limited to specific regions, but rather indicates widespread environmental awareness with a growing demand for political action (EU, 2021; UNDP, 2021). However, the relationship between industry-led political philanthropy and the spread of scientific misinformation sows polarisation around climate change, influences public attitudes towards climate change, and exerts control over political processes (Farrell, 2019). This has implications for teaching decisions about how and whether to introduce controversy in the classroom, particularly in value-conservative contexts (Long et al. 2022).

Whether a teacher should be reserved and politically 'neutral' or whether he or she is allowed to take a stand is controversially discussed in literature (e.g. Hess & McAvoy, 2015; Wohnig, 2020). The positions vary from a general commitment to the values of human and children's rights to a clear advocacy of individual standpoints as well as the disclosure of personal normative foundations and reference points. Despite these different positions, there is a consensus that teachers need to be aware of their role and responsibility and that own normative stances and attitudes need to be reflected (Hess & McAvoy, 2015; Wohnig, 2020). In German-speaking countries – and hence important for the geographical context of this study – the 'Beutelsbach Consensus' (Christensen & Grammes, 2020) serves as a kind of pedagogical safety net for teachers to adhere to the principles of political education. These are not to overwhelm students, to treat controversial issues as controversial, and give weight to the interests of students. If teaching is experienced as indoctrination of desired values and behaviour, this can trigger a negative reaction (a so-called boomerang effect) not only among students (Hörsch et al. 2023) but also among pre-service teachers. Effective CCE should therefore allow to take up the issue of controversy in teacher education and to critically deal with complexity, uncertainty, and contradictions. Such teaching has a positive effect on learners' behaviour (Boeve-de Pauw et al. 2015). However, there is little evidence in the literature about how teachers' attitudes differ and how this affects the way they approach controversy in the classroom.

Climate-related attitude types

A deep understanding of an audience's prior-knowledge and perspectives including beliefs and attitudes regarding a specific issue is essential in education (e.g. Vosniadou & Brewer, 1992). Knowing a target audience's opinions about climate change helps educators design programs addressing beliefs about climate change and how they influence teaching decisions (e.g. Drewes et al. 2018; Leiserowitz et al. 2021; Walsh & Tsurusaki, 2014). For example, Long et al. (2022) argue based on Kahan (2013) and McCright & Dunlap (2011) that teaching about climate change demands attention to cultural-psychological conditions as these conditions shape conceptions and learner identities. With the aim of developing strategies for effective and targeted climate communication for different audiences, the *Global Warming's Six Americas* was developed in 2008 by researchers at Yale and George Mason Universities. This framework segments the US public into six distinct, but internally consistent audiences based on beliefs, attitudes, policy preferences and behaviour regarding climate change (Maibach et al. 2011). The changes in the groups have since then been tracked twice a year using representative surveys (e.g. Leiserowitz et al. 2021). According to the representative survey of US citizens by Leiserowitz et al. (2021), the following distribution emerges in the USA in 2020: alarmed (26%), concerned (29%), cautious (19%), disengaged (6%), doubtful (12%) and dismissive (8%), with the 'alarmed' having the highest and the 'dismissive' the lowest belief in Global Warming (Figure 1). Comparable analyses on climate-related attitude types of other countries also showed that the public generally have a high level of climate awareness (see also EU, 2021 and UNDP, 2021) and can be distinguished

Figure 1. Audience segments in the USA, Australia, and Germany (data retrieved from Leiserowitz et al. (2021), Metag et al. (2015), and Morrison et al. (2013)). Note that comparison is limited due to differences in the survey items and data analyses between the countries.

by different patterns of information use and receptivity to climate-related information (Metag et al. 2015; Morrison et al. 2013).

Methodology

The research questions RQ 1 to 3 were addressed using a qualitative research approach based on oral narratives. In July 2020, during the Covid-19 pandemic, data was collected after pre-service teachers participated in a ten-hour online course unit on 'Teaching Climate Change'. This unit was part of an elective module in 'Natur, Mensch, Gesellschaft' (i.e. nature, human, society – largely corresponding to social and natural sciences) in the last semester of a single-phase, seven-subject bachelor's degree programme for primary teachers at the Zurich University of Teacher Education in Switzerland. The participants included nine pre-service teachers (four females and five males) who volunteered from a group of 20 students enrolled in the optional social and natural sciences course. Participation was voluntary and they were free to withdraw without consequence. At the time of the interviews, all had successfully completed the seminar and the final examinations. They were about one month away from starting as fully qualified and self-directed teachers, having to navigate the relative openness of the Swiss curriculum with their knowledge and skills. The interview guide was based on Keller-Schneider's (2020, 151) perception and stress-resource theory based professionalisation approach. To stimulate rich narratives related to the perceived demands of teaching climate change, the semi-structured guide was deductively differentiated according to thematic components of teaching climate change (Breitenmoser & Keller-Schneider, 2022). All interviews were conducted online due to contact restrictions. Each interview, varying from 46 to 73 min, was transcribed manually from Swiss dialect into German, following Dresing and Pehl (2015), and translated into English for analysis.

The fully anonymised data were initially analysed using content structuring qualitative content analysis as suggested by Kuckartz (2016). In a first step, the statements were deductively assigned to the upper categories based on the stress and resource theory-based model (Keller-Schneider, 2020, 151) and thematically differentiated for this study. Subcategories were then developed

from the material inductively. This process revealed specific beliefs and values about teaching and learning controversial aspects of climate change. The inductively developed category system was reviewed and adjusted by the author team after coding three interviews. Subsequently, all nine interviews were coded by the first author of this article using the revised category system. The detailed category system is available in the Supplementary Materials in Breitenmoser and Keller-Schneider (2024).

For this paper, we employed a second-order analysis step, wherein all material was deductively coded using Kuckartz's evaluative categorisation based on the Global Warming's Six Americas' framework (Maibach et al. 2011) (see Table 1). This involved classifying the pre-service teachers evaluatively into one of the six attitude types, based on most codes per person. To ensure the validity of this classification, three interviews were second-coded by a trained student assistant. The achieved intercoder reliability (Kappa = 0.88, calculated according to Brennan and Prediger (1981)) suggests a high level of consistency in the coding process.

Results

In the following sections, we present the climate related attitudes and approaches of pre-service teachers towards teaching climate change, structured around the three research questions (RQ 1–3).

The alarmed

In exploring the first research question, the 'alarmed' type prominently features in the statements of the pre-service teachers S1 and S7. For instance, S1, an active member of Greenpeace, articulates a clear intention:

'I want to show the children that we as humans have to change to combat the climate crisis [...] and that they can actively shape and change their future. [...] For me as an adult, the focus is on concrete actions in everyday life, not on running around at demonstrations. That does nothing for the climate.' (S1)

The 'alarmed' type manifests itself in expressions of concern and conviction regarding the urgency of climate change, primarily attributed to human activity. S1 and S7's awareness and informedness are evident in their emphasis on individual responsibility towards climate-conscious behaviour and support for climate protection measures in the private sphere.

In addressing RQ 2, the data reveals a conflict among pre-service teachers about the pedagogical implications of teaching controversial aspects of climate change in relation to their own values and understanding of teaching goals:

'Because what do I accept and demand from the children and what do I not, for example when it comes to recycling PET bottles on the school grounds? Where do I bring in my point of view? What is relevant to me and what is socially important? [...] Actually, I want to motivate the children to change their lifestyle. But I know that in my role as a teacher, I must be careful that I don't impose my opinion too much. But I can make them think.' (S1)

From this statement, it becomes evident that the topic of climate change is perceived as highly relevant for teaching. The overarching goal identified is to raise awareness about climate change among primary school students. S1 and S7 place significant emphasis on the role of individual actions in areas like recycling, energy, nutrition, and consumption. They voice a preference for practical, everyday measures over public-sphere actions, as illustrated in S1's statement above. S1 and S7 also want to encourage students to think critically and to foster an informed decision-making process: *'So that they can really understand the issue and form their own informed opinions and actions'* (S7). To facilitate this, S1 and S7 want their students to gain a foundational understanding of climate change. They value discussions, debates, and

Table 1. Excerpt from the codebook. The definition of the categories is based on Maibach et al. (2011).

Code	Definition of category	Anchor examples	Number of codes per student S1–S9
Alarmed	Human-caused only; major, current threat; very concerned; very well informed, high level of interest; keen to change own behaviour; strongly support climate action	<i>Climate change affects all areas of life, somehow. It is a highly topical issue. More and more natural disasters are now happening because of climate change. [...] I think the climate strikes are good. You can then discuss the issue with people. (S7)</i>	S1(7); S4(5); S5(4); S7(9)
Concerned	Mainly human-made; major threat, but not top priority; concerned; well informed, interested; little effort to change own behaviour; supports most climate protection measures	<i>I think climate change is a very important issue to deal with. But I'm pretty sure that if I'd been at the climate demonstrations, it would have been even more important to me. (S4)</i>	S1(2); S2(3); S3(4); S4(6); S5(8); S6(3); S7(2); S8(4); S9(2)
Cautious	Uncertain whether natural processes are also involved; threat in the future; not directly personally affected; somewhat informed, little interest; not eager to change own behaviour; only partially in favour of climate protection measures	<i>I think that climate change would take place anyway because it would just get warmer. It's not just because people are destroying the world, but I once read something by a super-smart researcher. I think he came up with that. I don't know whether it's true, but maybe not only humans are responsible for it. Humans make it larger, but I have the feeling that this would also happen in nature. – Just perhaps slower, but I am not completely sure. (S8)</i>	S2(8); S3(2); S5(3); S6(11); S8(7); S9(2)
Disengaged	Mostly not being aware; little informed; little climate awareness	<i>No examples in the data</i>	–
Doubtful	Mainly natural processes; little concern; low threat; little climate-conscious behaviour; rejects most climate protection measures	<i>I acknowledge that there is something about the warming. But maybe in ten years everything will be different again and the earth will regulate itself. [...] I don't know what to believe. But I don't believe everything I hear. [...] I have no expert knowledge. For this reason, I use my common sense and the knowledge that is still tangible and real and try to form my own opinion. [...] I and the majority are not willing to renounce anything. [...] As long as the perfect solution [no renunciation] does not exist, there is no point. (S9)</i>	S9(5)
Dismissive	Rejection that man-made; not concerned at all; no threat; no climate-aware behaviour; rejects climate actions	<i>No examples in the data</i>	–

philosophical conversations as methods to encourage evidence-based opinion formation, especially on the controversial aspects of the topic. However, they express uncertainty regarding the actual implementation of these ideals in a classroom setting.

RQ 3 examined the motivational factors and barriers influencing pre-service teachers' intentions to teach climate change. Emotional involvement in climate issues emerged as a significant challenge:

'It is difficult to remain emotionally neutral on issues that affect me very much. [...] But it should be made clear to the children that a teacher also has an opinion. But this is not central for the children, because they should learn to form their own opinions and to justify them. [...] But at the end of the day, I think that it is the children themselves who form the opinion that is strongest and that can be best justified with facts.' (S7)

S7 acknowledges in this statement a strong personal belief but recognized the necessity of maintaining a degree of emotional neutrality to encourage independent opinion formation among students. Moreover, the importance of introducing various perspectives in the classroom is emphasised in statements of S1 and S7, ensuring students to form their own well-founded opinions. Although they acknowledge that the scientific community largely agrees on the human-induced climate change, they note the diverse opinions present in society. Parents may have different beliefs, but according to S1 and S7, this does not influence their teaching. They refer to the curriculum and the Federal Constitution as a legitimising basis for teaching climate change. At the same time, S1 and S7 believe that it ultimately depends on a teacher's convictions and interests whether climate change is taught, as the following statement clearly indicates: *'Everyone has to decide this for themselves and justify it with the curriculum'* (S7). This is made challenging by the perceived lack of pedagogical content knowledge to teach the topic.

The concerned

In exploring the first research question, the 'concerned' type prominently features in the statements of the pre-service teachers S3, S4, and S5. Like the 'alarmed' type, they describe climate change as a problem for society, but overall, they have less confidence in their own knowledge and ability to teach the issue, as S5 expresses: *'I need to learn more because I still know too little to teach it'*. The respondents show support for climate protection measures, but tend to favour simpler, universal solutions.

For RQ 2, the statements reflect the importance of a neutral stance on teaching climate change:

'I would not teach the subject as passionately as climate activists, which is good. That way the children are not emotionally overwhelmed' (S5); and *'I have a neutral attitude. Therefore, I can deal with the topic objectively and factually, i.e. without moralising or indoctrinating values.'* (S4)

This neutral stance is perceived to be essential by the pre-service teachers, as teaching the topic requires a balanced approach. In addition, they agree that teachers should act as role models for sustainable behaviour, while also maintaining neutrality on divisive subjects to prevent indoctrination, moralization, and emotional overload of students. The aim of climate education at the primary level should be to *'instil basic knowledge that enables students to form an informed opinion'* (S3). The emphasis is on promoting open-mindedness, the acceptance of diverse opinions, and an awareness of the finite nature of resources. They further highlight the importance of students to understand that individual restrictions and actions in the private sphere, even if seemingly insignificant, play an important role in combating the climate crises. Hence, the students should learn about the contribution they can make as individuals.

In terms of RQ 3, the implementation of controversial aspects in the classroom is described as challenging. S5 voices a concern: *'I constantly feel I am doing something wrong. Even if the science was 100% certain, there are still different ideologies regarding the climate crisis.'* This

hesitancy is also reflected in S3's comment: *'Addressing it in the classroom is delicate because it requires constant reflection and great care what and how I say something to whom. I cannot meet this demand.'* This uncertainty also extends to the professional role of the teacher and how to deal with normativity. The pre-service teachers are unsure how to discuss such content with the children. Conflict is seen as something negative in the classroom and is avoided.

The pre-service teachers agree that no concrete instructions for action should be given and all viewpoints need to be respected. They believe that students should adopt a critical perspective, using the information provided to make their personal choices. There is, however, no clear idea of how to incorporate norms, responsibility, and individual action in the classroom. One primary challenge these pre-service teachers face is the different opinions that students might come with, often shaped by media and parental influences. They fear that these perspectives differ from theirs and might negatively influence the lesson and they are afraid of giving wrong information on controversial issues. This leads to uncertainty when dealing with students' questions.

A lack of practical experience in discussing such current and emotionally charged issues in class further complicates the matter. A solution, as proposed by the 'concerned' pre-service teachers, revolves around focusing on the scientific perspective using *'proven, objective teaching materials to justify my decision to teach climate change'* (S4). This ensures accurate and neutral teaching, as underscored by S3:

'I would like to leave out emotional aspects and discussions about controversial topics outside as much as possible and focus on objectivity and correctness so that the students are not overwhelmed, and the teacher is not moralising about the measures.' (S3)

However, they also admit that potential confrontations with parents and the school community discourage them from discussing controversial topics. The fear of damaging relationships and facing criticism is evident in S3's and S4's statements:

'It's a front I don't want to get in between as a teacher [...] It's outside my comfort zone' (S3) and *'If the parents and the school don't want me to do it, then my hands are kind of tied and I would refrain from doing it for selfish reasons because I don't want to cause problems and jeopardise the relationship with the parents. I don't want to take that risk.'* (S4)

Consequently, despite recognizing the importance of addressing climate change, these pre-service teachers are wary of introducing controversial content into their lessons, thereby sidelining potential learning opportunities.

The cautious

In exploring the first research question, the 'cautious' type is reflected in the statements of the pre-service teachers S2, S6, and S8. These pre-service teachers acknowledge human-induced climate change, yet they also express uncertainty about the role of natural processes. In addition, the pre-service teachers express insufficient basic knowledge and a low level of interest in the topic. They perceive climate change primarily as a distant threat and express limited support for mitigation measures, stating the absence of effective solutions.

Addressing RQ 2 for the 'cautious' type, the focus of teaching is on promoting unbiased and differentiated opinions among students, emphasizing that there are no strictly 'right' or 'wrong' opinions. They underscore the importance of students engaging with diverse perspectives and what they can do about it to not merely echoing media headlines. S2 articulates this approach as follows:

'Students should learn what they can do concretely, e.g. dispose of glass and PET bottles or turn off the light when leaving the room. Something small, without being insanely restrictive and that is not controversial, but positive.' (S2)

The aim is to promote actions that are non-controversial yet positively impactful for the environment, thereby enhancing student self-efficacy to *'do things like that'* (S8). However, S8 voices a concern that while children may aspire to save the planet, individual efforts of children are futile. He wants to show these students that, once they can vote, they can make a difference. At the same time, teacher credibility is rooted in being reflective role models, but S6 questions the equity of holding teachers to stringent standards when others in society might not be accountable. According to S2, it is important not to impose restrictive measures on students unless there are good and workable solutions for all.

Several challenges are expressed in teaching climate change by the pre-service teachers (RQ 3). A significant concern is the difficulty in maintaining neutrality, especially on emotionally charged topics like climate change. They express worries about the influence of personal biases arising from personal guilt linked to unsustainable lifestyles and the potential of inadvertently indoctrinating students. Even when teachers strive to be objective, it is difficult to convey sound facts without personal bias.

Both S6 and S8 express doubts about climate education, citing ambiguities in current scientific evidence and the prevalence of dissenting views. Their statements indicate a struggle with the complexity of the issue and the conflicting information available. S6's comment, *'I wouldn't be happy if I taught something that I wasn't completely convinced of and I wasn't sure if it was right. That's what holds me back the most'*, encapsulates this sentiment. The possibility of a teacher with rigid views influencing students' perceptions inappropriately is worrying them. As S8 puts it, there is uncertainty if a passionate climate activist teacher *'with an extreme opinion can adequately consider the other side and teach the issue objectively'*. It is emphasised that a good teacher should point out contradictions and that this is easier if the teacher has a neutral attitude and a less extreme opinion. S2 vocalizes a *'fear that I might indoctrinate the children because the issue in society is very much dependent on personal opinion and the willingness to want to change something, which is less tied to facts.'* To navigate this, S2 wishes for mandated teaching materials that are both scientifically accurate and devoid of extreme stances: *'I would like to have a framework on how to talk to children about controversial issues without extreme positions dominating'*. Furthermore, in order to work and cooperate well with parents, privacy should be respected. As S6 shares: *'I don't want to go out on a limb and tell the children and parents that they can no longer fly. I don't want to make a big deal out of it.'* This group also highlights the influence of media on children and the negative, emotionally charged nature of climate coverage. They advocate for protecting children from distressing topics in the classroom. Consequently, they prefer introducing non-controversial topics such as 'forest' as a foundation for more complex discussions at higher school levels.

The doubtful

The 'doubtful' type manifests itself in the statements of S9 (RQ 1). This pre-service teacher's statements reveal a conflicted stance on climate change, acknowledging its existence, yet expressing strong doubts about its causes. S9 describes a reluctance to accept the consensus among climate scientists and a hesitation to endorse individual or political actions aimed at mitigating climate change. Lifestyle changes or restrictions are particularly unpalatable to S9.

The pre-service teachers' views on teaching controversial aspects of climate change reveal varying educational priorities and approaches (RQ 2). S9's perspective is illustrated through a personal anecdote involving a student's reaction to a speech by Greta Thunberg:

'A third-grader told me after the weekend that she felt good because she had heard a speech by Greta. Surely, a third-grader is not ready to understand that yet! She probably got it from her parents. I don't impose my opinion on anyone. But as a teacher, you should also show the children that not everything Greta or the climate experts say is right and not everything the climate sceptics say is right either. It's important to me that the children don't accept everything they hear about climate change without checking it out, but that they learn to

think critically and to believe what is right and important to them. This is not necessarily what their parents say or what the media reports.’ (S9)

S9 emphasises that he does not want to impose his opinion on anyone and elaborates on the importance of critical thinking and not accepting information at face value, whether from teachers, media, parents, or (public) figures like Thunberg. S9’s focus in school is on neutrality and presenting all sides of the debate, while intending to foster critical thinking.

In terms of RQ 3, S9 expresses uncertainty on the topic and a distrust of scientific knowledge. He says that it is difficult to teach something as true when there are many different opinions and it is not proven what is true. He describes himself as *‘objective, factual, and neutral,’* but expresses strong convictions. He describes it challenging to provide students with an unbiased view and highlights the importance of using neutral teaching materials that might sometimes conflict with one’s personal beliefs. Moreover, finding such balanced resources that also take up *‘other than mainstream scientific knowledge’* can be demanding. If he were to discuss climate change, all sides of the controversy would need to be explored to give students an objective view. He notes that addressing climate change has no priority for him as the search for such *‘neither extremely pro nor con texts’* involves too much time and effort. Moreover, S9 believes primary school students to be too young to understand different perspectives and to form their own, unbiased opinions. The pre-service teacher concludes with a sentiment of uncertainty: *‘I don’t know what to teach the children, because I don’t want to just say that – they say this, the others say that’*, reflecting upon a conflict between personal beliefs and professional responsibility.

Discussion and implications

This section will discuss along the three research questions of this study how Global Warming’s Six Americas’ attitude types evidenced in pre-service teachers’ statements express varied perspectives and approaches to teach climate change, including aspects of neutrality, controversy, and contextual influences.

Global Warming’s Six Americas attitude types evidenced in the pre-service teachers’ statements (RQ 1)

In our sample of nine pre-service teachers, we identified the following distribution of the groups: *‘alarmed’* (S1, S7), *‘concerned’* (S3, S4, and S5), *‘cautious’* (S2, S6, and S8), and *‘doubtful’* (S9). [Table 2](#) compares the distribution of the identified types in our study with the representative survey of US citizens in 2008 (Maibach et al. 2011) and 2020 (Leiserowitz et al. 2021) and for Germany with survey data from 2011. Two types (disengaged and dismissive) could not be characterised by the evaluative coding in this study. In accordance with our findings, the *‘dismissive’* type could not be distinguished in Germany either (Metag et al. 2015). But despite the limited sample sizes, differences in the analyses, and the year of the sampling, the proportion of pre-service teachers in this study is comparable to that of the US and German populations, particularly for the *‘alarmed,’ ‘concerned,’* and *‘doubtful’*.

Teaching controversial aspects (RQ 2)

A strong emotional attachment to the issue is manifested in the statements of the *‘alarmed,’* yet these pre-service teachers emphasise that they want to teach it in a (politically) neutral way. Only pre-service teachers in this group reflect upon their own privacy and their role as a teacher. According to them, a professional teacher, must not overpower and manipulate students

Table 2. Comparison of the proportion of pre-service teachers in this study with the US population in the Six-Americas (Leiserowitz et al. 2021; Maibach et al. 2011) and for the Five-Germans classifications (Metag et al. 2015).

	Alarmed	Concerned	Cautious	Disengaged	Doubtful	Dismissive
This study ($n=9$)	2	3	3	–	1	–
Leiserowitz et al. (2021) ($n=1006$)	26%	29%	19%	6%	12%	8%
Maibach et al. (2011) ($n=2164$)	18%	33%	19%	12%	11%	7%
Metag et al. (2015) ($n=3000$)	24%	18%	28%	20%	10%	–

but must reflect clearly that teaching can never be neutral. Teachers should instead support students in learning about different solutions to combat the climate crisis by taking different perspectives, argue, judge, compare, discuss, and debate. However, they describe private sphere actions. Moreover, they fear that they will not be able to meet the demand for neutrality in every teaching situation which they relate to a lack of teaching experience and pedagogical content knowledge, including assessment skills. In contrast to the findings of Seow and Ho (2016), we found no evidence that teachers in the ‘alarmed’ group were reluctant to introduce controversy because they did not want to confuse their students.

More than in any of the other groups, dealing with controversy in the classroom is among the topics of greatest concern to the ‘concerned’. In contrast to the ‘alarmed’, these pre-service teachers describe themselves as neutral both personally and in their teaching. Scientific knowledge, the political centre, and not having a firm opinion are equated with neutrality. Not being neutral is often equated with being moralising and the indoctrination of values. Thus, these pre-service teachers see themselves as best suited to teach the issue. However, by focusing on objectivity and neutrality, the political dimension of the controversy is unconsciously avoided. This approach to dealing with controversial issues has already been described by Hess (2004) as the ‘avoidance’ type. Besides, emotionality is largely avoided to focus on perceived objective scientific facts in the classroom. This is linked to an expressed need for control and security. Controversy means uncertainty and insecurity. They experience fears of introducing controversial aspects in their classrooms, especially in relation to parents, despite research showing that most teachers had never experienced such pressure (Plutzer et al. 2016; Wise, 2010). It can only be hypothesised why these pre-service teachers perceive climate change as a much greater threat than studies have shown. But parents represent an unsettling and unpredictable factor for teachers, amplifying the uncontrollable effects of their teaching.

In contrast to the ‘concerned’ who describe a desire to be emotional neutral, the ‘cautious’ and ‘doubtful’ feel emotionally attached to the issue. However, they describe a guilty conscience or annoyance which makes it difficult to remain neutral in the classroom. In contrast to the ‘alarmed’ and ‘concerned’, the ‘cautious’ and ‘doubtful’ describe climate change as not only ethically but also scientifically controversial. Consequently, these pre-service teachers want to present as many aspects of the debate as possible on an equal footing so that the students can form their own opinions. As a strategy for dealing with the claim of neutrality, these groups emphasise scientific and ethical controversy in the classroom without favouring any position. Like the findings by Hess and McAvoy (2015) and Nation and Feldman (2021), even the largely uncontroversial scientific aspects of the topic are presented as ‘one opinion among many’ because they underestimate the scientific consensus on the human-induced climate change (Plutzer et al. 2016). It also remains unclear how the media coverage and informal contexts in recent years have changed teachers’ perception as pre-service teachers are exposed to climate change often in controversial ways (Allgaier, 2019; Farrell, 2019). Our findings support the conclusion by Long et al. (2022) that the assessment of the scientific consensus is not only related to perceived content knowledge but is intertwined with teachers’ political attitudes and values about climate change and its causes. Teaching about climate change is closely linked to the context as it shapes the perception of the requirement to teach climate change (Breitenmoser & Keller-Schneider, 2024). As the ‘doubtful’ type reflects, it is essential that ‘we’ should not take

science seriously as ‘they’ (climate experts) are not always right. This raises the problematic question of what teachers then use to evaluate facts and statements if not science. This misconception must be addressed in teacher education as teachers need to become aware of their own beliefs as a reference system for evaluating facts and their own professional role as a teacher. Therefore, teaching ‘wicked problems’ (Rittel & Webber, 1973) requires a clear distinction between the scientific knowledge about what we know and how, and ethical questions in the normative dimension about what future we want and what we should do (Hess & McAvoy, 2015). Colston and Vadjunec (2015) propose – for at least in conservative contexts – that taking up ‘both sides’ of the controversy might be an entry point to engage conservative learners with scientific knowledge, avoiding boomerang effects. While this may be a fruitful pedagogical approach in very value-conservative contexts and for ‘climate deniers’, we agree with Hess and McAvoy (2015) and Wohnig (2020) that this is not the case for the majority of learners. The majority of learners show high support for climate action in general (EU, 2021; Leiserowitz, et al. 2021; UNDP, 2021), as evidenced by the absence of the dismissive type in our data.

While the ‘alarmed’ refer to the curriculum and the Sustainable Development Goals as a form of legitimacy for addressing the topic and the ‘concerned’ think it is a ‘too hot topic to address in the classroom’, the ‘cautious’ and ‘doubtful’ do not see climate change as an educational mandate. These pre-service teachers emphasise that the inclusion of the topic in the classroom is primarily a matter of opinion and depends on teachers’ attitudes. This finding is consistent with Plutzer et al. (2016) and Seow and Ho (2016), who highlight that the willingness to address controversial aspects in the classroom depends on the teacher’s value commitments. Moreover, the salience of a topic (i.e. its importance, significance, or urgency), influences the attention paid to it. Higher salience leads to greater focus on the topic. The pre-service teachers in this study are consistent in their statements about their own attitudes as well as their statements about others, showing motivated reasoning (Kahan, 2013). They agree that high salience is associated with strongly held beliefs and attitudes towards an implementation in the classroom. There is also agreement that the way in which controversial aspects of the issue are addressed in the classroom is related to the political attitude of the teacher. While the pre-service teachers describe dealing with neutrality and controversy in the classroom as challenging for themselves, but at least fundamentally feasible, they do not trust colleagues from the left or right of the political spectrum to deal with controversial issues in the classroom in an ‘objective’, ‘factual’, and ‘neutral manner’. Climate sceptics are accused of ignorance and a lack of scientific evidence in the classroom, while climate activists are accused of ignoring different opinions, failing to take a ‘neutral stance’, and indoctrinating students through moralising. However, we found no evidence in our data that the ‘alarmed’ ignore different opinions. They rather explicitly reflect upon their beliefs and their professional role as a teacher. On the other hand, the ‘doubtful’ distrust science and use their own beliefs implicitly as a reference system. For all, neutrality is seen as a goal and has only positive connotations, regardless of the context. Not having a strong opinion is associated with the political centre and is equated with neutrality.

Motivation, challenges, and barriers and their influences on teaching controversial aspects of climate change (RQ 3)

Our results can be interpreted considering Dängeli and Kalcsics (2018) findings that (political) controversy and dissent in schools are often associated with the concept of conflict, which has negative connotations in everyday life. This is consistent with the described desire of being neutral through non-involvement and non-interference in the private sphere by the teachers. Strikingly, none of them reflected upon neutrality in education. If teachers are to strengthen children’s self-confidence, self-esteem, and self-regulation, teachers are intervening in the privacy of children. As a result, institutionalised political struggles to negotiate solutions from different perspectives remain unrecognised, respectively undesirable.

Although all pre-service teachers in our study state to follow the principles of the Beutelsbach Consensus (Christensen & Grammes, 2020) and are hence aware of the problem of indoctrination, they describe a lack of content and pedagogical content knowledge to deal professionally with their own values and beliefs, and thus with controversial aspects in the classroom. In line with our findings, Baumann and Niebert (2022) conclude from a study conducted with geography students that teachers based their lesson design on their own beliefs and values about sustainability, rather than on their own professional penetration of the topic. The results of this study also support this finding, but they show a differentiated picture across the different groups despite the small sample size. Overall, the pre-service teachers consider aspects, such as changing perspectives, forming different opinions, and critical thinking to be of high pedagogical relevance. But the interconnectedness of different value dimensions is perceived as a challenge as Spiropoulou et al. (2007) have already described. This lack of expertise to deal with different opinions, complexity, and controversy in the classroom with a lack of content knowledge contributes to a great deal of uncertainty. However, it is the perceived challenges related to the teacher's professional attitude towards neutrality and controversy that lead the pre-service teachers to avoid controversy in the classroom. Gayford (2002) and Plutzer et al. (2016) came to a similar conclusion. According to their findings, it is the non-scientific aspects that prevent teachers from addressing socio-scientific issues. For most teachers, teaching climate change is about conveying scientific facts about the issue (Kranz et al. 2022). Hence, we strongly urge to put the controversy where it really is. Various surveys (e.g. EU, 2021; Leiserowitz et al. 2021; UNDP, 2021) including our results have shown high support for climate protection in general, but there is a controversy when it comes to specific protection measures.

Also, learning opportunities in the sense of political education under the aspect of sustainable development were not perceived by the pre-service teachers. Climate change has been addressed only indirectly, if at all, in the context of environmental education with a focus on individual behaviour change. This indicates the extent to which the problem and responsibility are shifted to the private sphere, rather than also being seen as a systemic problem requiring public sphere solutions (Stern, 2000). Our findings are consistent with studies showing that CCE in schools tends not only to focus on scientific facts but also on private sphere actions such as turning off lights or recycling (e.g. Kranz et al. 2022; Nicholls, 2016). The integration of the political, social, and ethical dimensions, as well as a collective approach, are hardly considered (Kranz et al. 2022; Waldron et al. 2019). These measures in the private sphere are generally considered less controversial in society but at the same time, they are problematic because these actions run the risk of moralization (e.g. 'I am a better person because I fly less'). Likewise, action orientation is misunderstood as giving instructions for action (Baumann & Niebert 2022), which leads to anxiety about no longer being neutral as a teacher and intervening in the privacy of children and parents.

In summary and across all groups, a teacher's ability to teach controversial issues is associated with a neutral stance. A professional teacher must be 'neutral', i.e. have no fixed opinion and rely on objective scientific facts (especially 'concerned') or take all positions into account (especially 'cautious' and 'doubtful'). Neutrality can be interpreted as an underlying fear of positioning oneself as a teacher and as to where indoctrination starts. Neutrality is associated with uninfluenced formation of opinion. Similarly, neutrality is seen as a protection against being drawn into conflicts, especially with parents. Furthermore, neutrality and controversy are individually interpreted by the pre-service teachers and are understood differently in different contexts. Aspects of neutrality, such as emotional, moral, ethical, political, social, or scientific, are unspecifically intertwined. From the perspective of the pre-service teachers, meeting the demand for neutrality is challenging and complex, perhaps because they misinterpret neutrality. For the pre-service teachers, neutrality (in all its aspects) is a maxim for action and an inherent value, regardless of the context. However, value neutrality can be problematic. Neutrality can degenerate into indifference, but this is not perceived by the

pre-service teachers. While neutrality is sought and uncritically valued positively, controversy is negatively valued and avoided in the classroom. According to Christensen and Grammes (2020), the debate about restraint and (supposed) neutrality is described as a 'misconception, as the principle of controversy does not mean "neutrality"' (Christensen & Grammes, 2020, 15). Teachers such as the 'concerned', who supposedly have no opinion, feel insecure or avoid reflecting on their values, can thus run counter to the concerns of Global Citizenship Education. According to Wohnig (2020), there can be no neutral political education [Politische Bildung], just as education is not neutral. According to the author, central to the political dimension in education is the reference to the normative guidelines of human and children's rights. Nor can the whole complexity, with all its arbitrary points of view and without corresponding analysis and criticism, be placed side by side with equal emphasis in the classroom, from which students are supposedly allowed to choose 'neutrally' (Hess & McAvoy, 2015; Wohnig, 2020). In addition, we propose to include the normative guidelines of sustainable development in climate education. The teachers in our study often deal with everyday ideas in a very relativistic way and do not describe them as misconceptions or as normative. However, certain statements, such as contemptuous of humanity ones, must be labelled as unethical or wrong on the basis of scientific knowledge. Opinion forming requires – besides knowledge – exposure to different (but not arbitrary) point of views.

In our sample, controversy is not seen as a learning opportunity and the political dimension of climate change is avoided. Approaches of classical environmental education are preferred (Baumann & Niebert 2022) despite that the public sphere could relieve teachers of the moral burden of private sphere actions in climate education. Particularly among the pre-service teachers in the 'concerned' group, the focus is on science-oriented teaching. Socio-political aims such as adequate participation in democratic, social decision-making processes are not recognised. Thus, there is no reflection on the different interests and needs of individuals and groups as well as on social norms and values. These are necessary for a change of perspective and for the empowerment of self-determined, critically-reflective, and evidence-based decision-making in a world characterised by uncertainty and normativity (Rittel & Webber, 1973). In contrast, a teacher should act as a facilitator of the learning process, triggering and addressing uncertainty. Moreover, the focus of CCE should be on socio-scientific issues. Pre-service teachers need to learn that it is not about resolving controversies, but how they can deal with them to encourage their students to change perspectives, evaluate different points of view, and, if necessary, to position themselves to arrive at a well-founded, evidence-based opinion. According to Kissling and Bell (2020), understanding the global climate crisis requires scientific expertise, but dealing with it requires active, informed (young) citizens.

Limitations

The main limitations of the study relate to sampling and the sample size. As the pre-service teachers were enrolled in the course taught by the principal investigator of this study, a bias in the statements due to familiarity with the lecturer and first author of this article cannot be ruled out. However, at the time of the interviews, there was no longer a lecturer-student relationship. The pre-service teachers had all finished their final exams and were about to start teaching as fully qualified and self-directed teachers. To ensure objectivity and reflexivity, reliance was placed on peer-reviews (Trowler, 2011). Furthermore, due to the exploratory approach of the study, the sample size was limited to nine pre-service teachers. The extent to which these findings can be replicated in larger samples should be explored. Finally, the Global Warming's Six Americas framework was tailored for the US and for the general public. There is no equivalent tailored segmentation for Switzerland nor for pre-service teachers. However, the framework has been successfully extended to other countries such as Germany (Metag et al. 2015) or Australia (Morrison et al. 2013).

Implications for an audience-specific climate change communication and future research

Plutzer et al. (2016) highlight that enhancing teachers' scientific knowledge alone is inadequate for effective CCE. Instead, varying attitudes and beliefs among citizens, classified into distinct climate types by Maibach et al. (2011), necessitate adapted communication strategies in teacher education. These strategies should address the diverse needs and requirements of teachers, enabling them to tackle controversial aspects professionally when teaching climate change.

The 'alarmed' could be engaged in their consumer role and taught a critical understanding of global issues focussing on the public sphere. This involves in-depth content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge for pre-service teachers, especially in handling controversial topics and incorporating Global Citizenship Education. Others, like the 'concerned', who express the greatest degree of uncertainty and prefer 'neutrality', may benefit additionally from best practice examples and teaching materials. The 'cautious' group, characterised by moderate engagement, could be approached with narrative-based communication to increase the relevance of the subject matter. For the 'cautious' and 'doubtful', confronting political ideas, fake news, and values in the context of scientific consensus and political negotiation is crucial. Likewise, all teachers need to be trained in how to bring controversy into the classroom without overwhelming students. Teachers must learn to teach evaluation skills so that they can differentiate, lead and enable their students to relate 'neutral' scientific facts to values.

Plutzer et al. (2016) and Hörsch et al. (2023) warn university instructors against 'boomerang effects' in teaching, where promoting a particular view might strengthen opposition. Waldron et al. (2019) suggest a critical, open, and holistic approach to CCE, combining cognitive and affective elements for social transformation. This calls for a pluralistic, reflective, and critical examination of normative values and beliefs, linked to scientific, social, economic, and political aspects of climate change, catering to different target groups.

We understand the implications of our study as an initial step towards audience-specific climate change communication in higher education. Future research should explore how different target groups use and are impacted by content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge and attitudes towards climate change and how teaching materials can support the professional development of (pre-service) teachers, especially concerning the public sphere.

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Informed consent statement

This study was conducted with pre-service teachers and their participation was voluntary. Their contributions to the empirical data have been fully anonymized. To recognize themselves in this publication, they were assigned a pseudonym.

Disclosure statement

The authors report that there are no competing interests to declare.

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